

Anomaly Detection in Grid Compute Nodes: A Machine Learning Approach Leveraging HEP Benchmark Suite

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

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Detecting anomalies in the performance of Grid compute nodes presents a formidable challenge that has been addressed through various methodologies over the past decades. A recent innovative approach, pioneered by the HEPiX Benchmarking Group in the last few months, introduces a novel dimension to this pursuit. This method leverages the power of the HEP Benchmark Suite (HEP-Suite) to scrutinize and validate the performance metrics of Grid compute nodes in relation to fabric metrics.

By executing the HEPsuite tool on the grid, a substantial dataset of performance metrics has been meticulously compiled. Preliminary investigations have already indicated the promising potential of utilizing this data for constructing an anomaly detection system.

Considering the extensive volume of collected metrics (features), a more profound analysis could significantly benefit from the application of advanced machine learning techniques. The objective of the summer student project is to assess the impact of these features on the computational efficiency of job slots. This involves a focused exploration of critical configurations through an in-depth analysis of the extensive dataset.

The project involved deep engagement with benchmarking processes, utilizing the capabilities of HEPscore23, and developing a machine learning model specifically tailored for comprehensive parameter correlation analysis. This work provided the opportunity to make significant contributions to cutting-edge research while gaining a comprehensive understanding of high-energy physics computational frameworks.

ABSTRACT

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This report explores the challenge of detecting anomalies in the performance of Grid compute nodes within the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG). Using the HEP Benchmark Suite (HEP-Suite), the study explores how machine learning techniques can be applied to automate the detection of performance issues, on different CPU models. The report highlights the use of SCiForest, an improved version of the Isolation Forest algorithm, which is particularly effective at identifying both global scattered and clustered anomalies. Validation metrics such as the Jaccard Index, F1 Score, and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) were used to evaluate the performance of SCiForest. The results show that SCiForest is effective in detecting clustered anomalies, though some false positives remain, indicating areas for further improvement. The report suggests continuing this research by testing additional machine learning algorithms, such as the XGBoost outlier detection algorithm, to improve detection accuracy. This ongoing work is important for ensuring the continued performance and reliability of the computing infrastructure that supports critical experiments at CERN.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Benchmarking is a crucial process in evaluating the performance of systems or components, such as smartphones or CPU models. Just as consumers compare smartphones based on benchmark scores to find the best option for their needs, benchmarking in computing allows for the comparison of servers and CPU models using predefined tasks or workloads. This helps determine which system or component offers the best performance for specific tasks, guiding informed decision-making.

In the field of high-energy physics (HEP) and the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) [1], benchmarking is essential for comparing CPU performance across different countries. The WLCG, which supports CERN's large-scale experiments, relies heavily on efficient computing power. Benchmarking ensures that the computing resources allocated to these experiments are both effective and sufficient, directly influencing financial planning and resource allocation. CPU power is often quantified by multiplying the benchmark score by the number of seconds a given application is used [2].

The HEP Benchmark Suite [3] is specifically designed to meet the benchmarking needs of the WLCG. It consists of three primary packages:

- **HEP-Workloads:** This package provides the tasks used to measure CPU performance.
- **HEP-Score:** It calculates a benchmark score, known as HEPscore by taking the geometric mean of the results from the HEP-Workloads tasks.
- **HEP-Benchmark-Suite:** This package coordinates the benchmarking process and compiles the results into a standardized JSON file for further analysis.

One of the latest configurations, **HEPScore23** [2], has been officially adopted by the WLCG. It includes seven workloads derived from five major experiments ATLAS [4], CMS [5], ALICE [6], Belle II [7], and LHCb [8]. The structure and components of these packages are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Diagram of the HEP Benchmark Suite, illustrating the workflow for configuring, running benchmarks, processing data, and publishing results [9].

Benchmarking in WLCG is not just about evaluating performance, it also plays a key role in resource allocation among countries. Each country contributes computing resources based on the size of its research community, either through direct funding or by providing equipment. Instead of focusing on cost alone, the WLCG uses the CPU power delivered by each site as a standard measure. This ensures that resource contributions are fairly evaluated and helps in planning and distributing computational resources efficiently [2].

2. PROBLEM DEFINITION AND APPROACH

The HEP Benchmark Suite, currently in use on the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG), has evolved to include more than just performance metrics. With the integration of various plugins, the suite can now collect user-defined metadata, such as server load, memory usage, and power consumption. Among these, the load per core is particularly significant, as it can be correlated with the HEPscore per core, a measure of a server's performance. By plotting these two metrics against each other in a 2D scatter plot, it is possible to identify patterns that reveal the performance of the computing infrastructure. Specifically, this plot can highlight anomalies, such as misconfigured servers or underperforming hardware, which may not align with expected performance levels. However, the current approach to anomaly detection within this context is manual and time-consuming. Analysts must repeatedly review these plots, searching for deviations that indicate potential issues. This repetitive task not only consumes valuable time but also introduces the possibility of human error. The goal of this project is to automate the anomaly detection process using machine learning techniques. By training models to recognize patterns within the scatter plots, it becomes possible to efficiently and accurately identify anomalies, thereby improving the overall reliability and performance of the WLCG [10].

To illustrate the concept, a scatter plot of HEPscore per core versus load per core is provided (see Figure 2), where each point represents data from a different site but using the same CPU model. By analyzing the distribution of these points, it is possible to identify anomalies - sites where the server load and performance do not align as expected, potentially indicating a misconfiguration or other issues. The correlation between HEPscore per core and load per core serves as a key feature in the unsupervised learning approach. This relationship will be leveraged in the later stages of the project to build a machine learning model capable of identifying anomalies across different sites in an automated and efficient manner, as described in the following sections.

Figure 2. Scatter plot of HEPscore per Core vs. Load per Core for one CPU model (AMD EPYC 7452 32-Core Processor) across different sites, with marginal distributions shown along the top and right axes for each site.

3. TYPES OF ANOMALIES

a. GENERAL TYPES OF ANOMALIES

Understanding the different types of anomalies is essential for effective anomaly detection in performance benchmarking. According to Han et al. (2022) [11], as shown in Figure 3, anomalies can be categorized into several types, each exhibiting unique characteristics:

- **Local Anomalies:** These are deviations from the normal data that occur within a local neighborhood. They are identified by comparing data points within a small, localized area, making them distinct from the surrounding data.
- **Global Scattered Anomalies:** These anomalies are significantly different from the normal data and are spread far apart from each other. Generated from a uniform distribution, they represent data points that are uniformly distant from the normal data distribution.
- **Dependency Anomalies:** These occur when the dependency structure of the data is violated. In other words, the features of the data are expected to have a certain relationship, and when this relationship is not followed, a dependency anomaly is identified.
- **Global Clustered Anomalies:** Also known as group anomalies, these are clusters of data points that deviate from the normal data distribution. They exhibit similar characteristics and are often grouped together, away from the trendline of normal data.

Figure 3. Visualization of four common types of anomalies in datasets highlighting the differences in how normal data points (blue) and anomalous data points (red) are distributed [11].

In the context of the HEP Benchmark Suite and the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG), identifying anomalies is essential for maintaining the efficiency and reliability of the computing infrastructure. Specifically, the anomalies we focus on include global clustered anomalies and global scattered anomalies:

- **Global Clustered Anomalies:** These anomalies are characterized by a group of data points that deviate together from the expected trend. In the WLCG dataset, this is typically observed when multiple servers from the same site show abnormal behavior, such as consistently lower or higher HEPscore relative to their load per core.
- **Global Scattered Anomalies:** These are isolated data points that deviate significantly from the expected performance but do not form a cluster. In the WLCG dataset, these scattered points usually represent servers with individual misconfigurations rather than systematic errors.

For this analysis, the primary focus is on identifying global clustered anomalies, as they are indicative of larger systemic issues that could affect multiple servers or sites. The scatter plot of HEPscore per core versus load per core is a useful tool for visualizing these anomalies. In the scatter plot presented in Figure 4, points that are far from the trendline represent potential global clustered or scattered anomalies.

Figure 4. Types of Anomalies in WLCG Grid Nodes for a selected CPU model (AMD EPYC 7542 32-Core Processor), showing global clustered and scattered anomaly regions.

b. TYPES OF CLUSTERED ANOMALIES IN BENCHMARKING DATA

Clustered anomalies can be categorized into three main types: underperformance anomalies, overperformance anomalies, and 'other' anomalies.

- **Underperformance Anomalies**

Underperformance anomalies are identified by clusters of data points that fall below the general trendline in a scatter plot of HEPscore per core versus load per core. These anomalies indicate that certain servers or nodes are delivering less computational power than expected, given their load. This type of anomaly could be due to hardware degradation, misconfigurations, or inefficiencies in the system (example in Figure 5).

- **Overperformance Anomalies**

Conversely, overperformance anomalies are characterized by clusters of data points that fall above the general trendline. These indicate servers or nodes that are performing better than expected under a given load. While this might seem beneficial, overperformance can sometimes signal an issue, that could lead to inconsistent resource allocation or misleading performance metrics.

- **Other Anomalies**

The third type, other anomalies, are more complex as they identify a part of the site as abnormal. These anomalies are often indicated by a 'flat area' of data points on the scatter plot, where the trendline for the site differs significantly in slope compared to the general trendline for the CPU model. In such cases, the slope might be nearly horizontal, indicating a lack of expected performance scaling with increased load (example in Figure 5).

Figure 5. Types of clustered anomalies with highlighted types of anomalies.

4. MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS FOR ANOMALY DETECTION

Anomaly detection in large-scale datasets requires robust and efficient machine learning algorithms. Among the many available algorithms, two have shown particular promise: Isolation Forest [12] and Split-Selection Criterion Isolation Forest (SciForest) [13]. These algorithms are particularly effective at detecting both global scattered and clustered anomalies, making them well-suited for the complex data involved in HEP benchmarking, especially due to the data distribution and the anomaly regions with both types of global anomalies.

a. ISOLATION FOREST

Isolation Forest is a popular anomaly detection algorithm known for its effectiveness in identifying global scattered anomalies. The algorithm works by isolating observations in the feature space using random splits along hyperplanes. This process, which involves recursively partitioning the data, is particularly effective at identifying outliers that are sparsely distributed across the dataset. The key advantage of Isolation Forest lies in its ability to generalize well across different types of data distributions. By relying on random splits, it can quickly and efficiently isolate anomalies that differ significantly from the majority of the data, particularly when those anomalies are scattered rather than clustered [12].

b. SPLIT-SELECTION CRITERION ISOLATION FOREST

Split-selection Criterion Isolation Forest is an enhanced version of the standard Isolation Forest algorithm. While Isolation Forest excels at detecting global scattered anomalies, SciForest is designed to improve the detection of both global scattered and clustered anomalies. The primary innovation in SciForest is the use of a selection split criterion based on data statistics rather than purely random splits. This method involves selecting hyperplanes that better separate local distribution peaks within the data, allowing the algorithm to more effectively isolate clusters of anomalies. By focusing on areas where data points are densely packed, SciForest can detect subtle variations that might indicate a clustered anomaly. In the training stage of SciForest, multiple isolation trees are generated from random sub-samples of the data. Each tree is constructed by selecting separating hyperplanes that maximize the separation of data distributions at each recursive subdivision. The evaluation stage then measures the path length of each data point within the tree, with shorter path lengths indicating anomalies. This approach encapsulates the two key properties of anomalies: they are few and significantly different from normal instances, which typically have longer path lengths in the trees [13]. SciForest generalizes well, much like Isolation Forest, but its refined split-selection criterion makes it particularly effective at detecting clustered anomalies.

5. FEATURE SPACE TRANSFORMATION

In the context of anomaly detection for visual inspections using 2D scatterplots of HEPscore versus Load per Core, it is crucial to enhance the separation of potential anomalies from normal data points. The primary goal is to assist users in visually identifying anomalies on these plots, particularly since the machine learning algorithm applied for this task operates in an unsupervised learning model for each CPU model. To improve the clarity and effectiveness of this detection process, an additional feature dimension was introduced: the distance of each point from the trendline. By incorporating this distance as a new dimension, we can transform the feature space into a 3D scatter plot of Trendline Distance versus HEPscore versus Load per Core. Applying an unsupervised learning algorithm to this enhanced 3D feature space allows for better separation and identification of points that deviate significantly from the trendline in the original 2D scatterplot.

However, during the initial implementation, the machine learning algorithms tended to incorrectly classify points near the trendline as anomalies. These points, while close to the trendline, were located at the edges of the distribution along the trendline (see Figure 6a). This misclassification occurs because the points, despite their proximity to the trendline, fall on the outer bounds of the point distribution in the feature space, leading to false positive detections. To address this issue, an additional transformation of the feature space was introduced, defined by the formula 5.1.

$$\text{Load per Core Transformed} = \frac{\text{Load per Core}}{1 + \frac{1}{\text{Trendline Distance} + \epsilon}} \quad (5.1)$$

When the trendline distance, defined as the distance of a point from the general trendline on the scatter plot, is small, the transformation compresses the load values near the trendline, helping the algorithm avoid misclassifying these points as anomalies. Conversely, when the trendline distance is large, the transformation has little effect, preserving the separation of points further from the trendline. This approach helps reduce false positives while maintaining the algorithm's ability to detect true anomalies. However, one potential drawback is the compression of points close to the trendline, which could result in missing some true anomalies that are close to the trendline. Additionally, choosing the appropriate value for ϵ , which is a small constant to avoid division by zero, requires careful adjustment to balance these effects.

This transformation effectively squeezes the points close to the trendline together, thereby indicating to the algorithm that global anomalies are unlikely to occur in this region. As a result, the algorithm can more accurately focus on identifying anomalies in areas further away from the general trendline. The effectiveness of this transformation is illustrated in the following figures. In Figure 6a, a point marked in red is relatively close to the general trendline compared to other points, leading to a low value on the vertical axis. This point, along with others in similar positions, was often misclassified as an anomaly by the machine learning algorithms due to its position on the edge of the load feature distribution. After applying the transformation, as shown in Figure 6b, these points are squeezed closer together, which helps the algorithm correctly identify true anomalies based on larger distances from the trendline.

Figure 6. Feature space transformation in the Load per Core, HEPscore per Core, and Distance from Trendline feature space, showing parabolic and squeezed parabolic cylinder samples shapes.

By applying this feature space transformation, we provide the machine learning algorithms with a more refined dataset, enhancing their ability to detect true anomalies while reducing false positives associated with edge effects near the trendline. This approach was applied in the presented machine learning algorithms to improve the overall results.

6. RESULTS

In the context of anomaly detection for the WLCG, Isolation Forest is effective at detecting global scattered anomalies. However, it sometimes struggles with identifying global clustered anomalies, which are critical for ensuring the accuracy of the system’s performance assessment (see Figure 7). SCiForest, an improved version of Isolation Forest, addresses this limitation by being more effective at detecting global clustered anomalies. Given the importance of identifying these clustered anomalies in our analysis, SCiForest is the preferred choice (see Figure 8).

Figure 7. Isolation Forest example results in the HEPscore per Core vs Load per Core scatter plot.

Figure 8. SCiForest example results: detected clustered anomalies in the HEPscore Residuals plot.

a. MORE SPLIT-SELECTION CRITERION ISOLATION FOREST RESULTS

Since our goal is to detect global clustered anomalies, the SCiForest algorithm was chosen. In Figure 9 example results for different CPU models are presented (different scatter plots), with anomaly points marked with a black point border.

Figure 9. SCiForest example results in the HEPscore per Core vs Load per Core scatter plots, with anomaly points marked by a black point border.

It can be observed that all clusters identified as potential anomalies were correctly detected by the SCiForest algorithm. However, there are instances where the algorithm also classifies individual points as anomalies that do not form clusters, or where points within a cluster are spaced far enough apart that they may be identified as scatter anomalies.

Figure 10. SCiForest example results in the HEPscore per Core vs Load per Core scatter plots, with partially misclassified anomaly points.

On the other hand, the algorithm struggles to correctly identify anomalies for a small number of CPU models. Figure 10 presents examples of misclassified anomalies. It can be observed that the algorithm identifies points that are relatively close to the trendline as anomalies, whereas for other CPU models, these would not be classified as anomalies. These are examples of false positives. Despite this, the results obtained for all CPU models are promising, and the performance of the algorithm, especially for an unsupervised learning approach, is satisfactory.

b. VALIDATION

To evaluate the performance of SCiForest, we used a set of labeled anomalies for both global clustered and global scattered types. Not every CPU model exhibited anomalies, so the validation was focused on those models where anomalies were present. The results were assessed using several key metrics: the Jaccard Index, F1 Score, and Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC).

- **Jaccard Index:** This metric measures the similarity between the predicted anomalies and the ground truth. It is calculated as the size of the intersection divided by the size of the union of the two sets. A Jaccard Index of 0 indicates no similarity, while a value of 1 indicates perfect similarity. This metric is particularly useful for evaluating the overlap between predicted and actual anomalies.

$$Jaccard\ Index = \frac{|y_{pred} \cap y_{true}|}{|y_{pred} \cup y_{true}|} \tag{6.1}$$

- **F1 Score:** The F1 Score balances precision and recall, providing a single measure that accounts for both false positives and false negatives. It ranges from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates perfect precision and recall, and 0 indicates poor performance. This metric is critical in ensuring that the algorithm is not only accurate but also consistent in its predictions.

$$F1\ Score = 2 \cdot \frac{Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall} \tag{6.2}$$

- Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC):** The MCC is a comprehensive measure of binary classifications, taking into account true and false positives and negatives. It is considered a balanced measure even in cases where the classes are of very different sizes. An MCC of 1 indicates a perfect prediction, 0 indicates random prediction, and -1 indicates total disagreement between prediction and observation. This metric is particularly important in scenarios where both types of errors (false positives and false negatives) need to be minimized.

$$MCC = \frac{TP \cdot TN - FP \cdot FN}{\sqrt{(TP+FP) \cdot (TP+FN) \cdot (TN+FP) \cdot (TN+FN)}} \quad (6.3)$$

TP – True Positive
TN – True Negative
FP – False Positive
FN – False Negative

The SCiForest algorithm was thoroughly evaluated using labeled anomalies for both global clustered and global scattered types. Since not every CPU model exhibits anomalies, the validation was specifically conducted on those CPU models where anomalies were known to be present (smaller number of CPU models with clustered type of anomalies). This focused approach allowed for a more accurate assessment of the algorithm's performance in detecting the relevant anomalies. The results of SCiForest's anomaly detection are illustrated in Figure 11 and Figure 12, which show both the combined predictions for clustered and scattered anomalies, as well as the predictions for only clustered anomalies. For a significant number of CPU models, the predicted results closely matched the labeled anomalies, indicating that SCiForest effectively identifies the types of anomalies.

However, it is important to note that there were still some false positives in the results. These false positives had a noticeable impact on the performance metrics, slightly reducing the overall scores. While there is still room for improvement, particularly in minimizing false positives, the algorithm has shown that it is a robust tool for detecting global clustered anomalies, which are the primary focus of this analysis.

Figure 11. Validation results for the global clustered type of anomalies, with CPU models sorted in ascending order for each respective metric (Jaccard Index, F1 Score, Matthews Correlation Coefficient).

Figure 12. Validation results for the global clustered and scattered type of anomalies, with CPU models sorted in ascending order for each respective metric (Jaccard Index, F1 Score, Matthews Correlation Coefficient).

7. CONCLUSIONS

This report presents a comprehensive analysis of anomaly detection in Grid compute nodes using machine learning techniques, with a specific focus on the HEP Benchmark Suite and the WLCG infrastructure. The use of SCiForest, an enhanced version of the Isolation Forest algorithm, proved effective in detecting global clustered anomalies, which are critical for ensuring the reliability and efficiency of the computational resources in the WLCG. The application of SCiForest demonstrated improvements in reducing false negatives, a key metric in anomaly detection, while maintaining a reasonable balance with false positives.

The validation process using metrics such as the Jaccard Index, F1 Score, and Matthews Correlation Coefficient confirmed the effectiveness of SCiForest in identifying relevant anomalies. However, the presence of false positives and false negatives indicates that there is still room for improvement, particularly in refining the algorithm's ability to distinguish between normal and abnormal data points. Due to time constraints, a quantitative comparison between the different algorithms was not made, but this should be the first step going forward to substantiate the observed improvements.

Moving forward, it is recommended that this analysis be extended by incorporating additional machine learning algorithms. The integration of anomaly scores derived from unsupervised learning algorithms as input features for subsequent models could further enhance the detection accuracy. Specifically, the application of the XGBoost outlier detection algorithm, augmented with additional anomaly labels, appears promising based on the data analysis conducted. Such an approach could leverage the strengths of SCiForest while addressing its limitations, potentially leading to even more robust and precise anomaly detection.

In conclusion, the findings from this report underscore the value of advanced machine learning techniques in managing the complex and distributed computational environment of the WLCG. By continuing to refine these approaches and exploring new algorithms, it is possible to further improve the detection and resolution of anomalies, thereby ensuring the sustained performance and reliability of critical high-energy physics experiments.

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